

Nira variety - a susceptible host for mass rearing rice thrips *Srenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall)

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Peak infestation of rice by thrips occurs during late Jul-Oct and Jan-early Apr in the Philippines. For a continuous supply of thrips to screen rice germplasm for resistance and for associated basic studies, suitable rice varieties are needed for thrips mass rearing. We evaluated thrips population growth on varieties Nira, Dawn, TN1, Pankhari 203, IR42, TKM6, Rexoro, and Kinanda (all considered susceptible) and Dahanala 2220 (resistant).

Three-week-old seedlings of each variety grown in pots (15-cm-diam) at 5 seedlings/pot were infested with 5 pairs of male and female thrips and covered with snug-fitting mylar cages, with 5 replications/entry. Eggs, larvae, prepupae, pupae, and adults on each plant were counted 14 d after infestation (DI).

Increase in thrips population was significantly higher on Nira; Dahanala 2220 had the lowest population (see table). The suitability of Nira for thrips mass rearing was further evaluated by exposing to natural thrips infestation potted Nira plants at 15, 20, 30, 40, and 50 d after transplanting. Regardless of plant age, no significant differences in thrips establishment were observed. Even older Nira plants could be used to maintain a thriving thrips culture year-round. □

Populations of thrips *S. biformis* on different rice varieties.^a IIRRI, 1986.

Variety	IIRRI acc. no.	Thrips ^b (no.) at 14 DI
Nira	6309	56 a
Dawn	02029	41 b
TN1	105	37 bc
Pankhari 203	5999	33 bcd
IR42	36959	28 bcd
TKM6	237	24 cd
Rexoro	143	23 cd
Kinanda	3882	18 d
Dahanala 2220	50730	0.60 e

^a Av of 5 replications. ^b From 25 pairs of males and females. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Effect of insecticide treatment at different rice crop stages on carry-over of yellow stem borer (YSB)

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YSB larvae hibernating in rice stubbles can carry over infestation if continuous cropping is practiced. We studied the effect of insecticides applied at various crop growth stages on the intensity of hibernating larvae. The 2-season

Effect of insecticides applied at different crop stages on YSB carry-over. Navsari, India, 1986 summer and wet season.

Treatment ^a	Hibernating larvae (no.)/10 stubbles per plot		
	1986 summer	1986 wet season	Pooled
Maximum protection	4.0	2.2	3.1
Maximum protection except in seedbed	4.8	3.2	4.0
Maximum protection except at vegetative stage	4.8	3.2	4.0
Maximum protection except at reproductive stage	5.3	4.0	4.6
Maximum protection except at ripening stage	4.4	2.9	3.6
Seedbed protection only	9.0	6.8	7.9
Vegetative stage protection only	7.8	5.8	6.8
Reproductive stage protection only	5.3	3.6	4.4
Ripening stage protection only	6.8	4.8	5.8
Control (no protection)	9.6	7.8	8.7
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.3	0.3

^a Maximum protection = seedbed protection: carbofuran 3 G at 0.5 kg ai/ha 5 d before transplanting; vegetative stage protection: foliar spray of monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.036% at 5 and 25 d after transplanting (DT), application of carbofuran 3 G at 1.0 kg ai/ha at 15 DT, and foliar spray of fenitrothion 50 EC at 0.05% at 35 DT; reproductive stage protection: foliar spray of monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.036% at panicle initiation and flowering; ripening stage protection: foliar spray of monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.036% at soft dough stage.

Effect of some insecticide formulations against newly emerged yellow stem borer (YSB) larvae

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We conducted a laboratory experiment to determine the efficacy of some insecticide formulations against newly emerged larvae of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas*. Aqueous 0.04%

experiment with 10 treatments was in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Larval population after harvest was determined by splitting 10 randomly selected stubbles from each treatment plot and counting the larvae found.

The number of hibernating larvae was lowest with the maximum protection treatment, followed by maximum protection except during ripening (see table). Other treatments had comparatively higher numbers of hibernating larvae. □

Effect of some insecticide formulations against newly emerged YSB larvae. Navsari, India.

Treatment	Formulation	Larval mortality ^a (%)
Monocrotophos	36 WSC	68.9
Fenitrothion	50 EC	65.9
Cypermethrin	25 EC	60.1
Carbaryl	50 WP	52.1
Chlorpyrifos	20 EC	63.1
Diazinon	20 EC	39.7
Methyl parathion	50 EC	61.6
Water	-	12.6
No treatment	-	8.4
CD (0.05)		1.4

^a Av of 3 replications. Data converted to angular values.

concentration solutions of 7 insecticidal formulations were applied as foliar spray on egg masses. Distilled water and no treatment were the controls. Egg masses were observed daily for 10 d.

Monocrotophos 36 WSC was most effective in killing newly emerged YSB larvae, followed by fenitrothion 50 EC and chlorpyrifos 20 EC (see table). □

Preference, oviposition response, and population growth of *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) on selected rice varieties

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Several rice varieties with resistance to thrips have been identified by mass screening at IIRRI. We compared thrips' preference, oviposition response, and population increase on varieties BJI, TKM6, ASD7, Dahanala 2220 (resistant check), and Nira (susceptible check).

Preference test. Pregerminated seeds of each variety were sown singly near the periphery of 30-cm-diam clay pots filled with paddy soil, with 10 pots/variety. At the first true-leaf stage, a small glass vial containing 10-cm-long rice leaf cuts with 100 thrips adults was placed in the middle of each pot, which was covered with a snug-fitting mylar cage. Thrips settling on each seedling were recorded at 1, 4, 16, 32, and 48 h after release.

Oviposition response. Five- to seven-day-old seedlings with roots wrapped in moist cotton were placed singly in 20 by 2.5 cm glass test tubes (5 tubes/variety) and infested with 5 pairs of newly emerged males and females. The adults were removed after 2 d and the eggs laid on each seedling counted.

Population increase. Three-week-old rice seedlings (5 seedlings/15-cm-diam pot) were infested with 25 pairs of newly emerged male and female thrips and the pots covered with a mylar cage. Thrips eggs, larvae, prepupae, pupae, and adults in each cage were counted 14 d after infestation.

In the preference test, thrips adults discriminated between susceptible and

Table 1. Percent of *S. biformis* adults that settled on seedlings of resistant and susceptible rice varieties 1, 4, 16, 32, and 48 h after infestation (HI) in a free-choice test. ^a IIRRI, 1987.

Variety	IRRI acc. no.	Adults (%) that settled on seedlings				
		1 HI	4 HI	16 HI	32 HI	48 HI
Dahanala (resistant check)	50330	3.2 c	0.9 e	0.9 d	1.8 d	3.5 c
BJI	256	34.2 a	27.8 b	25.3 b	22.8 b	21.5 b
TKM6	237	10.3 c	13.7 d	15.8 c	16.4 c	17.5 b
ASD7	6303	20.3 b	21.2 c	20.9 bc	17.5 c	19.7 b
Nira (susceptible check)	6309	25.3 b	35.9 a	36.8 a	40.7 a	36.1 a

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Av of 10 replications, 100 adults/pot.

resistant varieties soon after release (Table 1). At 1 h after release, significantly more adults had settled on susceptible Nira than on resistant Dahanala 2220. After 4 h or longer, significantly more adults were on Nira than on seedlings of other varieties; Dahanala 2220 was the least preferred.

Dahanala 2220 and TKM6 were the least preferred for oviposition; Nira was most preferred (Table 2). The population increase was highest on Nira and lowest on Dahanala 2220. Factors affecting resistance or susceptibility of rice varieties to thrips are being investigated. □

Table 2. Oviposition response and population increase of *S. biformis* on plants of resistant and susceptible rice varieties. ^a IIRRI, 1987.

Variety	Eggs laid (no./5 females) in 48 h	Thrips ^b (no.) at 14 d after infestation
Dahanala 2220 (resistant check)	0.3 d	0.2 d
BJI	1.2 c	17.2 b
TKM6	0.5 d	9.2 c
ASD7	2.1 b	18.2 b
Nira (susceptible check)	4.9 a	90.6 a

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Av of 5 replications. ^bFrom 25 pairs of males and females.

Ovicidal activity of insecticides against yellow stem borer (YSB)

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YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Wlk.) is an internal rice borer pest. Satisfactory control can be achieved by spraying a persistent insecticide with ovicidal activity. We laboratory-tested 7 insecticides — monocrotophos, fenitrothion, cypermethrin, carbaryl, chlorpyrifos, diazinon, and methyl parathion — at 0.04% concentration for their ovicidal activity against YSB.

YSB egg masses collected from ricefields were sprayed with aqueous solutions of insecticide. Control 1 was sprayed with distilled water and control 2 was untreated. The experiment was replicated three times.

Ovicidal activity of insecticides at 0.04% concentration against YSB. ^a Gujarat, India.

Insecticide	Unhatched eggs ^a (%)
Monocrotophos	63.2
Fenitrothion	33.4
Cypermethrin	15.6
Carbaryl	11.5
Chlorpyrifos	61.7
Diazinon	26.9
Methyl parathion	60.3
Control 1 (water spray)	8.1
Control 2 (no treatment)	6.0
CD (0.05)	0.5

^aAv of 3 replications. Data were converted to angular values.

Both treated and untreated egg masses were placed in petri dishes lined with moistened filter paper and observed daily for 7 d. Highest ovicidal activity was with monocrotophos, followed by chlorpyrifos and methyl parathion (see table). □